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Influence of Parenting Styles on Self-Concept of Pupils in Private Primary Schools in Makurdi, Benue State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of parenting styles on self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State. Four research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study, a review of related literature was done to find gaps, prove and back up findings. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of 18, 383 pupils in primary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. The simple random sampling technique was used to select 100 pupils that constituted the sample. The Parenting Styles and Self-Concept Questionnaire (PSSQ) was developed by the researchers and administered to gather data about pupils' self-concept. The questionnaire was made up of 20 items and followed the Likert modified four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options had numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, it was trial tested on 40 pupils. The scores obtained from the trial testing were subjected to analysis using Cronbach Alpha Correlation Coefficient. The analysis yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.75. The data were analysed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (X^2) goodness of fit test at .05 level of significance, with 2.50 serving as the criterion mean for decision making on the items to be responded to and below 2.50 was considered negative and disagree. The findings of the study were as follows; authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful parenting style have significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made among others; parents should encourage their children to express their thoughts and feelings and provide balanced feedback that promotes self-confidence and resilience. Also, parents should aim to reduce excessive control and harsh discipline, instead fostering a more supportive environment that values the child's opinions and feelings. This can help improve the child's self-esteem and self-worth.

Keywords: Parenting Styles, Authoritative Parenting Style, Authoritarian Parenting Style, Permissive Parenting Style, Laissez-faire Parenting, Style Self-concept

INTRODUCTION

The home is the first agent of socialization and parents are the masters. They determine how everything is done in the home and are also responsible for the provision of care, affection and also the basic necessities of life. Everything that the parents do in the home, including how they communicate, reward, punish or provide the physical, emotional, and psychological needs of their child is summed up to be parenting style. Parenting style is a pattern of attitudes that parents exhibit toward the upbringing of their children (Tam, Chong, Kadirvelu & Khoo, 2012). According to Gawas (2021) the term parenting style refers to the different methods that parents take into consideration to develop the social behaviors of their children. Parenting styles are also defined as all behavior issued by parents about good parenting, and their perceptions about their behavior towards children. In addition to their awareness of the nature of the relationship between them and their children.

According to Shahlal, Isa and Kecek (2021) the types of parenting styles were introduced by Baumrind (1967). The author classified parenting styles into three; authoritarian, authoritative, and permissive. Maccoby and Martin (1983) have extended the study of Baumrind (1967) as a result introduced another type of parenting style which is known as neglectful or uninvolved (Shahlal *et al.*, 2021). Parenting styles are distinguished by the level of demandingness and responsiveness exhibited by the parents. Demandingness refers to the extent parents control their children's behavior or demand their maturity while responsiveness refers to the degree parents are accepting and sensitive to their children's emotional and developmental needs. Parenting styles have a significant influence on the development of a child's self-concept, which refers to the way an individual perceives and evaluates themselves. This self-perception encompasses beliefs, values, abilities, and overall sense of identity (Noel, Kemeza, Kiaritha & Muhwezi, 2021).

Self-concept is an element that has evolved based on people's environment and the way they connect with social existence (Rahman, Shahrin & Kamaruzaman, 2017). It is related to the intellectual dimension of man or a woman, and also represents the individual's motion in the direction of himself or herself (Altaf, Hassan, Khattak & Iqbal, 2021). The self-concept has two broad domains; positive self-concept as well as negative self-concept. Positive self-concept entails knowing oneself, respect towards oneself, exhibiting positive and rational thinking and a firm sense of self in comparison to others. A negative self-concept included, negative evaluation of oneself, self-doubt, and sense of worthlessness and insecurity (Badgajar & Mundada, 2014). Altaf *et al.*, (2021) found in a study that self-concept was significantly related with parenting styles.

Authoritative parenting style is a child raising style depicted by a perfect equality of demandingness and responsiveness; and planning kids in a goal, issue-situated, restrained way by explaining the basis behind standards (Darko & Gyasi, 2019). Authoritative parents have high expectations for achievement and maturity, but they are also warm and responsive. Authoritative parents are characterized by being supportive, nurturing, and setting clear expectations. They also encourage independence while maintaining a structured environment. This style tends to foster a positive self-concept in their children. The parents encourage verbal give and take, share with the child the reasoning behind their policy, and solicit his objections when he refuses to conform. Both autonomous self-will and disciplined conformity are valued (Darko & Gyasi, 2019). Babbar and Dhankar (2021) found in a study that the types of parenting have a significant influence on the self-concept of students. In the study it proved that authoritative and authoritarian parenting styles have a strong positive relation to the students' self-concept. Children raised by authoritative parents often exhibit high self-esteem, a strong sense of autonomy, and a positive self-image. They are more likely to be self-reliant and capable of making independent decisions. The parents encourage verbal give and take, share with the child the reasoning behind their policy, and solicit his objections when he refuses to conform. Both autonomous self-will and disciplined conformity are valued (Darko & Gyasi, 2019).

The authoritarian parenting style is a child rearing style set apart by parental practices that are exceedingly prohibitive and exceptionally requesting. According to Darko and Gyasi (2019), the authoritarian parents shape, control, and evaluate the behaviour and attitudes of the child in accordance

with a set standard of conduct, usually an absolute standard, theologically motivated and formulated by a higher authority. High levels of parental control and low levels of responsiveness are the two characteristics of authoritarian parents. Although authoritarian parenting and authoritative parenting styles have similar names, they have several important differences in parenting belief, demand and approach. While both parental styles demand high standards, authoritarian parents demand blind obedience. They only allow one-way communication through rules and orders. Any attempts to reason with them are seen as backtalk. These parents use stern discipline and often employ harsh punishment, such as corporal punishment, as a way to control children's behavior. Authoritarian parents tend to be strict, controlling, and demanding. They often set high standards and may be less responsive to their child's emotional needs. Students raised in authoritarian households may have a more rigid self-concept. They might struggle with decision-making and may have lower self-esteem, as they may have been less encouraged to express their individuality (Shahlal *et al.*, 2021).

Permissive parenting style is a form of parenting where the parents are relatively non-controlling, make few demands on their children, allow them to make their own decisions, and regulate their own behavior (Uji, Sakamoto, Adachi & Kitamura, 2014). The permissive parenting style refuses to impose rules and standards but allows children's self-regulation. Parents act in an acceptant and affirmative manner towards the child's impulses and desires without punitive actions. Such children have a high level of freedom with no restriction of any behaviors if there is no physical harm. In this parenting style, the parents do not demand anything and expect little from their children. The parent-children relationship is at the friendship level with few limits imposed (Berg, 2011). Permissive parents are generally lenient and indulgent, setting few rules and providing a lot of freedom. They might be more responsive but less likely to enforce boundaries. Children from permissive backgrounds may have a less defined self-concept. They may experience difficulty with self-discipline and may have a tendency to be more impulsive. Permissive parenting style can cause a child to acquire disciplinary problems as well as low academic achievement. It is believed that the adolescents which are raised by this type of parenting style are typically immature in various psychosocial aspects (Babbar & Dhankar, 2021).

Neglectful or uninvolved parenting style is an undemanding and uncaring way of parenting a child. The idea of neglectful parenting style is identified by few parental demands, little communication and low responsiveness to their children. These parents usually disengage themselves from their children's life after fulfilling their basic needs. According to Williams and Sánchez (2012), uninvolved parents are self-involved or too busy, thus they can hardly provide the basic needs of food and shelter. They expect their children to take care of their own destiny. Parents of the parenting style show very little love, attention, mental and moral support, protection, and supervision to their children. Parents know very little about their children. It is because the parents do not spend much time with their child. Children from neglectful backgrounds may struggle with a negative self-concept. They may have difficulty forming strong interpersonal relationships and may face challenges in areas such as self-worth and self-efficacy (Thaib & Syah, 2019).

It is important to note that while parenting styles can have a significant impact, they are not the sole determinants of an individual's self-concept. However, in the current study, the focus is on children in primary schools. These population is in a critical and delicate stage of development, as they are still forming physically and psychologically. Therefore, the researcher aims to find out how specific parenting styles influence children's self-concept, based on pupils' perception of how their parents are raising them.

Statement of the Problem

Parenting is a process that involves fostering and supporting the physical, emotional, social and intellectual development of a child from childhood to adulthood. Children in the early years of life are delicate and can be easily affected by interactions that go on in the home directly and indirectly. And for children in primary schools, they might misunderstand actions taken by their parents towards them leading them to act in certain ways that may depict withdrawal and even a negative perception of themselves. As captured in the background to the study, parenting styles differ by way of the responsiveness and demandingness exhibited by parents and these affect offsprings. For example, the

researcher observed that a pupil once told said to “I am not intelligent” and when she enquired, she found out it came from a significant other in the home. And it happened because the child was being compared with another supposedly “more intelligent” child. Comments and actions like the above might be considered “normal” or “harmless” by parents or significant others but they have far-reaching consequences on the way children decode them and respond and they also constitute what is referred to as parenting styles. Therefore, in the current study, the researcher aims to find out the influence of parenting styles on self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does authoritative parenting style influence the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State?
2. How does authoritarian parenting style influence the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools?
3. How does permissive parenting style influence the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools?
4. How does neglectful parenting style influence the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Authoritative parenting style has no significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State.
2. Authoritarian parenting style has no significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools.
3. Permissive parenting style has no significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools.
4. Neglectful parenting style has no significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of 18, 383 pupils in primary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. The simple random sampling technique was used to select 100 respondents that constituted the sample. The number of participants was limited because of the population the researcher was dealing with. Considering the age and level of maturity of pupils the number was limited for ease of the research process. The Parenting Styles and Self-Concept Questionnaire (PSSQ) was developed by the researchers and administered to gather data about pupils' self-concept. The questionnaire was made up of 20 items and followed the Likert modified four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options had numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. The data were analysed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (X^2) goodness of fit test at .05 level of significance, with 2.50 serving as the criterion mean for decision making on the items to be responded to and below 2.50 was considered negative and disagree.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Research Question 1

How does authoritative parenting style influence the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State?

Table 1: Analysis of Influence of Authoritative Parenting Style on Self-Concept of Pupils in Private Primary Schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	My parents create a supportive space where I feel heard and understood.	0	55	20	25	2.30	.84	Rejected
2	My parents support me to learn from mistakes, boosting my confidence and potential.	21	54	9	16	2.80	.95	Accepted
3	My parents set rules with reasons, helping me understand consequences.	0	73	17	10	2.63	.66	Accepted
4	I feel confident in my ability to overcome challenges and succeed.	0	64	20	16	2.48	.75	Rejected
5	My parents' clear rules and explanations boost my confidence.	15	45	20	20	2.54	.93	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 2.55$ SD= .82								Accepted

Table 1 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 1 to 5 are 2.30, 2.80, 2.63, 2.48, and 2.54 with corresponding standard deviations of .84, .95, .66, .75, and .93 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 2.55 with the cluster standard deviation of .82 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that authoritative parenting style has influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

Research Question 2

How does authoritarian parenting style influence the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools?

Table 2: Analysis of Influence of Authoritarian Parenting Style on Self-Concept of Pupils in Private Primary Schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	My parents' strict rules leave me feeling punished for not meeting expectations.	65	25	10	0	3.55	.67	Accepted
7	Limited communication with my parents leaves me uncomfortable expressing myself.	1	73	16	10	2.65	.67	Accepted
8	I often feel pressured by my parents' high expectations.	0	40	29	31	2.09	.84	Rejected
9	I accept myself, but criticism, especially from my parents, can be tough.	0	80	16	4	2.76	.51	Accepted
10	I know myself, but sometimes I'm influenced by my parents' preferences.	0	61	19	20	2.41	.80	Rejected
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 2.70$ SD= .70								Accepted

Table 2 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10 are 3.55, 2.65, 2.09, 2.76, and 2.41 with corresponding standard deviations of .67, .67, .84, .51, and .80 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 2.70 with the cluster standard deviation of .70 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that authoritarian parenting style has influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

Research Question 3

How does permissive parenting style influence the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools?

Table 3: Analysis of Influence of Permissive Parenting Style on Self-Concept of Pupils in Private Primary Schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	My parents allow me freedom with minimal consequences for breaking rules.	32	43	4	2	2.86	1.09	Accepted
12	My parents act more like friends, offering little guidance.	28	51	3	18	2.89	1.01	Accepted
13	I'm often left to handle things alone as my parents don't intervene or set clear expectations.	35	42	8	15	2.97	1.02	Accepted
14	I have freedom, but lack guidance from my parents, impacting my identity and self-acceptance.	18	54	10	18	2.72	.96	Accepted
15	I have a clear understanding of my strengths and weaknesses.	38	37	5	20	2.93	1.12	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 2.90$ SD= 1.04								Accepted

Table 3 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 11 to 15 are 2.86, 2.89, 2.97, 2.72, and 2.93 with corresponding standard deviations of 1.09, 1.01, 1.02, .96, and 1.12 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 2.90 with the cluster standard deviation of 1.04 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that permissive parenting style has influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

Research Question 4

How does neglectful parenting style influence the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools?

Table 4: Analysis of Influence of Neglectful Parenting Style on Self-Concept of Pupils in Private Primary Schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
16	My parents' disengagement leaves me feeling lost and uncertain.	30	40	20	10	2.90	.94	Accepted
17	I feel good about myself, but lack of parental guidance sometimes makes me doubt my worth.	80	15	5	0	3.75	.53	Accepted
18	I know my strengths and weaknesses, but lack of parental involvement leaves me unsure of my potential.	40	45	10	5	3.20	.81	Accepted
19	I'm confident in overcoming challenges, but lack of parental support can lead to self-doubt	35	41	14	10	3.01	.94	Accepted
20	I accept both my strengths and flaws, but lack of parental attention makes self-acceptance challenging.	45	35	0	20	3.05	1.12	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.18$ SD= .90								Accepted

Table 4 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 16 to 20 are 2.90, 3.75, 3.20, 3.01, and 3.05 with corresponding standard deviations of .94, .53, .81, .94, and 1.12 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.18 with the cluster

standard deviation of .90 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that neglectful parenting style has influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Chi-square (X^2) was used to test the responses of respondents at .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Authoritative parenting style has no significant influence the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

Table 5: Chi-square Test of Influence of Authoritative Parenting Style on Self-Concept of Pupils in Private Primary Schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	47.760	.000	Sig.
SA	21	25.0					
A	54	25.0					
D	9	25.0					
SD	16	25.0					
Total	100						

Table 5 reveals that $\chi^2 = 47.760$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that authoritative parenting style has no significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools is rejected. This implies that authoritative parenting style has significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools.

Hypothesis 2

Authoritarian parenting style has no significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools.

Table 6: Chi-square Test of Influence of Authoritarian Parenting Style on Self-Concept of Pupils in Private Primary Schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	33.200	.000	Sig.
SA	1	25.0					
A	73	25.0					
D	16	25.0					
SD	10	25.0					
Total	100						

Table 6 reveals that $\chi^2 = 33.200$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that authoritarian parenting style has no significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools is rejected. This implies that authoritarian parenting style has significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools.

Hypothesis 3

Permissive parenting style has no significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools.

Table 7: Chi-square Test of Influence of Permissive Parenting Style on Self-Concept of Pupils in Private Primary Schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	127.440	.000	Sig.
SA	32	25.0					
A	43	25.0					
D	4	25.0					
SD	2	25.0					
Total	100						

Table 7 reveals that $\chi^2 = 127.440$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that permissive parenting style has no significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools is rejected. This implies that permissive parenting style has significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools.

Hypothesis 4

Neglectful parenting style has no significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools.

Table 8: Chi-square Test of Influence of Neglectful Parenting Style on Self-Concept of Pupils in Private Primary Schools in Makurdi, Benue State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	20.000	.000	Sig.
SA	30	25.0					
A	40	25.0					
D	20	25.0					
SD	10	25.0					
Total	100						

Table 8 reveals that $\chi^2 = 20.000$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that neglectful parenting style has no significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools is rejected. This implies that neglectful parenting style has significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this research was organized around the research questions and hypotheses for ease of reading and comprehension. The four null hypotheses that were postulated and tested were all rejected.

The first finding of the study revealed that authoritative parenting style has significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State. This finding implies that authoritative parenting, characterized by a balance of responsiveness and demandingness, fosters a supportive environment where children feel valued and understood. This approach encourages open communication, sets clear expectations, and provides consistent guidance, which helps children develop a strong sense of self-worth and autonomy. This finding is similar to that of Babbar and Dhankar (2021) whom found in their study that there was a significant positive relationship between authoritative parenting style and children’s self-concept. The nurturing yet structured nature of authoritative parenting helps pupils internalize positive self-images, enhancing their confidence, competence, and resilience (Darko & Gyasi, 2019). Consequently, these children are more likely to exhibit higher self-esteem and a clearer sense of identity, contributing to their academic and social success.

The second finding of the study revealed that authoritarian parenting style has significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools. This finding implies that the authoritarian parenting style can lead to children developing a negative self-concept, as they may internalize feelings of inadequacy, low self-worth, and helplessness. This is line with the findings of Wang (2015) and also Babbar and Dhankar (2021). The lack of emotional support and autonomy under authoritarian parenting can hinder the development of a healthy self-identity, causing pupils to struggle with self-esteem and confidence. Similarly, Altaf, Hassan, Khattak and Iqbal (2021) found that there was a significant negative relationship between authoritarian parenting style and self-concept, but however, posit that this relationship was moderated by gender. Consequently, these children might exhibit increased anxiety, submissiveness, and difficulty in social interactions, adversely affecting their academic performance and overall psychological well-being.

The third finding of the study revealed that permissive parenting style has significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools. This finding implies that, permissive parenting, characterized by high responsiveness and low demands, allows children considerable freedom and minimal regulation. While this can foster a sense of freedom and independence, it often lacks the structure and guidance necessary for developing self-discipline and a realistic self-assessment. This finding is in consonance with that of Rahman, Shahrin and Kamaruzaman (2017) who found that there was a negative relationship between permissive parenting style and the self-concept students in a study. Children raised in permissive environments may struggle with boundaries and self-control, potentially leading to an inflated or unstable self-concept. This can result in difficulties when facing challenges and criticisms, as they might not have developed the resilience and coping mechanisms that come from experiencing consistent expectations and constructive feedback. Consequently, while pupils may exhibit high levels of self-expression and creativity, they might also face issues with authority, persistence, and social interactions, impacting their overall academic and personal growth.

The fourth finding of the study revealed that neglectful parenting style has significant influence on the self-concept of pupils in private primary schools. Neglectful parenting, characterized by low responsiveness and low demands, often results in a lack of emotional support, guidance, and attention to the child's needs. This environment can lead to children feeling undervalued, unimportant, and isolated, severely impacting their self-esteem and sense of self-worth. The absence of parental involvement and encouragement deprives children of essential validation and feedback, crucial for building a positive self-concept. As a result, pupils raised in neglectful settings may struggle with feelings of insecurity, inadequacy, and a lack of direction. This finding is similar to that of Babbar and Dhankar (2021) who found that there was a negative correlation between the neglectful and uninvolved parenting style and self-concept. These children are also at a higher risk of developing behavioural problems, academic difficulties, and social issues, as they might lack the confidence and social skills fostered by more supportive parenting styles. The overall psychological well-being of these pupils is often compromised, underscoring the profound impact of neglectful parenting on their self-concept and life outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that parenting styles have significant influence on self-concept of pupils in private primary schools in Makurdi, Benue State. And the following recommendations were made;

1. Parents should encourage their children to express their thoughts and feelings and provide balanced feedback that promotes self-confidence and resilience.
2. Parents should aim to reduce excessive control and harsh discipline, instead fostering a more supportive environment that values the child's opinions and feelings. This can help improve the child's self-esteem and self-worth.
3. Parents should provide clear guidelines and expectations to help children develop self-discipline and a realistic self-concept, balancing freedom with responsibility.
4. Parents should strive to be more attentive and responsive to their child's needs, offering support, guidance, and validation. Building a stronger parent-child connection can significantly enhance the child's self-concept and overall well-being.

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